

Considering the FAIRness of your computational research

Illustration from Sonja Bezjak, April Clyburne-Sherin, Philipp Conzett, Pedro Fernandes, Edit Görögh, Kerstin Helbig, Bianca Kramer, Ignasi Labastida, Kyle Niemeyer, Fotis Psomopoulos, Tony Ross-Hellauer, René Schneider, Jon Tennant, Ellen Verbakel, Helene Brinken, & Lambert Heller. (2018). *Open Science Training Handbook (1.0)* [Computer software]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1212496>

Consider one of the following publications and evaluate the level of FAIRness of the methodology in your group. Pay specific attention to **data**, **software**, and the complete **analysis workflow**.

Paper 1	Paper 2
Codjia, E. D., Olasanmi, B., Ugoji, C. E., & Rabbi, I. Y. (2023). SNP-based marker-assisted selection for high provitamin A content in African cassava genetic background . <i>South African Journal of Science</i> , 119(11/12). https://doi.org/10.17159/sajs.2023/15115	Anna Niehues, Casper de Visser, Fiona A Hagenbeek, Purva Kulkarni, René Pool, Naama Karu, Alida S D Kindt, Gurnoor Singh, Robert R J M Vermeiren, Dorret I Boomsma, Jenny van Dongen, Peter A C 't Hoen, Alain J van Gool, A multi-omics data analysis workflow packaged as a FAIR Digital Object , <i>GigaScience</i> , Volume 13, 2024, giad115, https://doi.org/10.1093/gigascience/giad115

DATA

	Data FAIR Principles (https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/)	Data	Additional notes
F	Do the data and metadata have a unique and permanent ID (e.g. DOI) so it's easy to find and reference?		
F	Are the data described with plenty of clear information (metadata)?		
F	Does the metadata include the data's unique ID so people know which data it describes?		
F	Are the metadata and data easy to find in common online locations, like data portals or search engines?		
A	Can the metadata and data be accessed online via a standard method like a web link?		
A	Does the access method allow for authentication and authorisation where necessary?		
A	Is the metadata accessible, even when the data are not so that people know the data exist(ed)?		
I	In what format is the metadata and data shared? Is it readable and understandable, using generally available technology and knowledge?		
I	Do the metadata and data use standardised terminology or vocabularies so everyone can understand it?		
I	Do the metadata and data clearly link to other relevant data and metadata so that they fit into the bigger picture?		

	Data FAIR Principles (https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/)	Data	Additional notes
R	Are metadata and data released with a clear license explaining how it can be used?		
R	Do the metadata and data have a clear history (provenance) showing how and why it was collected or created? This refers to <i>provenance</i> .		
R	Do the metadata and data follow community standards, so others in the same field can easily work with them?		

Notes

SOFTWARE

	FAIR Principles for Research Software (https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x)	Software/ scripts	Additional notes
F	Does the software have a unique and permanent ID (like a DOI) so it can always be found?		
F	Do different software parts (modules/components) have a unique ID?		
F	Are different software/script versions assigned unique DOIs to ensure that users know which version they are using?		
F	Is there enough clear information (metadata) explaining what the software does, who made it, and how to use it?		
F	Do the metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the software/scripts they describe so that it's clear which software the metadata is about?		
F	Are the metadata FAIR, searchable and indexed?		
A	Can the metadata and software/scripts be accessed online easily (via a standardised communications protocol)?		
A	Does the access protocol allow for authentication and authorisation, where necessary?		
A	Is the metadata accessible, even when the software/scripts are not?		
I	Do the software/scripts work well with other software by sharing data and connecting through standard methods?		
I	Do the software/scripts handle data (read, write, share) in ways that follow standards		

	FAIR Principles for Research Software (https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x)	Software/ scripts	Additional notes
	used by others in the same field?		
I	Do the software/scripts link properly to other software, data, or essential information it relies on?		
R	Are the software/scripts usable (can be executed) and reusable (can be understood, modified, built upon, or incorporated into other software).		
R	Are the software/scripts described with lots of clear and useful information so others can fully understand it?		
R	Do the software/scripts have a clear license explaining what others are allowed to do with it?		
R	Is there a record of the software's history — who made it, how it was developed, and any important changes? This refers to <i>provenance</i> .		
R	Do the software/scripts clearly link to other software it depends on?		
R	Do software/scripts follow standards used by others in the same field, so they work well with other tools?		

Notes

WORKFLOWS

	FAIR Principles for Computational Workflows (https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-025-04451-9)	Workflow	Additional notes
F	Does each workflow version have a unique identifier (such as a DOI or permanent link) that makes it easy to find and refer to?		
F	Is the workflow described with enough information (metadata) so others can understand what it does and how to use it?		
F	Do the metadata mention the identifier, so it's clear which workflow and version the information belongs to?		
F	Are the metadata and workflow easy to find in common online places, like registries or repositories?		
A	Is the workflow and its components stored where anyone can try to access it using the identifier (even if they need special permission)?		
A	Does the way to access the workflow and metadata follow standard methods, so it works across different platforms?		
A	Is the metadata public even if the workflow is private or restricted, so people know the workflow exists?		
I	Do the workflow and metadata use common formats, tools, and languages to work well with other systems?		
I	Do the workflow and metadata use standard terms others already know (like from controlled vocabularies or ontologies)?		

	FAIR Principles for Computational Workflows (https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-025-04451-9)	Workflow	Additional notes
I	Is the workflow specified to allow its components to read, write, and exchange data (including intermediate data) in a way that meets domain-relevant standards?		
I	Does the workflow and metadata link to other relevant data and workflow components, so they fit into the bigger picture?		
R	Is the workflow well-described so others can understand and use it correctly?		
R	Is the workflow released with a clear and accessible license explaining how others can use it?		
	Is the workflow associated with information about who created them and their history (provenance)? (Can you cite it?)		
R	Does the workflow include references to other workflows?		
R	Does the workflow follow community standards, so comparing and combining with other workflows is easy?		

Notes
